

Computer modelling and simulation in clinics: Longitudinal mapping of usage and clinician's trust in *in silico* medicine

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INTRODUCTION: *In silico* medicine encompasses Computational Modeling and Simulation (CM&S) for disease prevention, diagnosis, prognosis, treatment, and biomedical product development. However, barriers still hinder the effective uptake of CM&S due to factors like regulatory gaps, limited training/resources, and stakeholder awareness. As the field of *in silico* medicine continues to evolve, it becomes imperative to understand perceptions, concerns, and expectations regarding its integration into clinical practice. To this end, we conducted longitudinal surveys, aiming to gather personal insights of clinicians, who are at the forefront of bringing CM&S for patients' benefit. **MATERIALS & METHODS:** The first online survey[1] was carried out between 2020 and 2021, the follow up survey was launched at the end of 2023 [2]. Both surveys counted about 25 questions, assessing among others, the level of awareness with CM&S techniques, trust, perceived barriers and opportunities for the uptake of *in silico* medicine. The second round probes deeper on trust levels and made available in multiple languages. **RESULTS & DISCUSSION:** Over 80% of the respondents from the first survey foresaw the need for CM&S expertise in their team. Interestingly, they counted on their positive personal experience over regulatory approval, to trust the evidence from CM&S. With a rapidly evolving domain, the follow-up survey aims to track changes in above trends. Moreover, capture a broader representation (different medical fields, geographies, demographics) including from those who have little or never experienced CM&S. Subsequently develop effective stakeholder engagement strategies.

REFERENCE [1] Lesage R, et al., (2023) Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey. *Front. Med. Technol.* 5:1125524. [2] Clinical outreach survey 2023: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/vphcs2a>

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